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Abstract. This article describes the problem of finding new techniques and ways to increase motivation for learning foreign languages. One of these forms is new pedagogical technologies, the implementation of which contributes to effective language learning. The article defines the concepts of "Pedagogical Technology" and "Smart Education", which are capable of providing a high level of education corresponding to the tasks and opportunities of today's world, will allow young people to adapt to a rapidly changing, unstable environment, will ensure the transition from book content to active content using a single common repository of educational materials with an analytical search system; an example of working with the site "die deutsche Welle" is given.

Key words: new information technologies, pedagogical technology, independent work, language social networks.

In recent years, pedagogical education has undergone major changes that cover almost all aspects of the educational process. The issue of using modern pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages is increasingly being raised. New methods and forms of teaching appear, which, in turn, represent not only various technologies of means of exchange and transmission of information, with the help of which the educational process is carried out, but also one large system of teaching methods aimed at developing students' communicative knowledge and improving their speech skills. The main task of a foreign language is to teach practical mastery of a foreign language, to form basic knowledge, that is, the ability to carry out foreign and international communication with native speakers. The search for new pedagogical technologies is associated with a lack of motivation among students to study a foreign language. Very often, positive motivation is absent, since when studying a foreign language, students face some difficulties and do not learn the material due to their psychological characteristics. Experience shows that the use of various, modern, fresh sources and means provokes interest in students, increases their motivation to study.

Pedagogical technology is a set of techniques, an area of pedagogical knowledge that reflects the characteristics of the deep processes of pedagogical activity, the features of their interaction, the management of which ensures the necessary effectiveness of the educational process [1].

The use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages allows for the reproduction of educational situations, helps to complement traditional teaching methods, promotes the formation of fundamental skills of foreign language communication from the awareness of the possibility of expressing thoughts in another language to the independent solution of communication problems, increases the desire and interest of students in learning, makes them look at the subjects being studied in a new way, thus revealing their creative and intellectual capabilities and talents.

At present, the concept of "SMART" is the main purpose of the development of educational systems. The main source of knowledge is electronic, educational Internet content, technological operations are providing feedback for teachers and students, and the exchange of knowledge between them.

Smart education is a concept that involves a comprehensive modernization of all educational processes, as well as the methods and technologies used in these processes [2]. SMART education is capable of providing a high level of education that meets the challenges and opportunities of today's world, will allow young people to adapt to a rapidly changing, unstable environment, and will ensure

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the transition from book content to active content using a single common repository of educational materials with an analytical search system. The quality of educational materials in the repository should be constantly monitored through the introduction of various materials and work in a single bundle with educational process management systems.

Considering current, innovative technologies, it is necessary to dwell in more detail on the topic of using Internet resources in teaching a foreign language. The possibilities of using online resources are enormous.

With the help of web resources, you can accomplish the following tasks:

- include online materials in the lesson content;
- conduct independent searches for information by students as part of working on a project;
- organize and develop reading skills and abilities using online materials of any complexity;
- improve listening skills based on audio texts from the online resources network;
- expand vocabulary with vocabulary and abbreviations of a modern foreign language;
- study the culture of a particular language [3].

At the moment, there are a large number of websites dedicated to independent study of foreign languages. On such websites, you can find ready-made lessons from foreign language teachers, exercises, audio recordings, grammar explanations that are incomprehensible to the student.

For example, M. G. Alekseeva, a teacher of German at the I. Yakovlev Chelyabinsk State Pedagogical University, actively uses the website "die deutsche Welle" in her work with students. As a rule, this website is very useful for independent work. It is a free German course that is suitable for both beginners and advanced users. The website offers a large selection of audio texts and videos of varying difficulty levels. School teachers of German can also use this material in their lessons. The advantage of the website is that it is simple and easy to use, which is why it is one of the best platforms for learning the language. To interest the listener, it offers famous talk shows, music videos, funny videos with hidden meanings, news, fascinating dialogues, etc. Using the exercises that are also available on this website, you can test your knowledge of German grammar and vocabulary and identify your weaknesses.

I would like to give an example of working with audio texts from the website "die deutsche Welle", which we visit quite often to complete various tasks in German. The recording of many texts lasts only 2 minutes, which helps the listener not get tired during this time, their attention does not wander and their interest does not disappear. One of the topics is called "Viele Köche verderben den Brei". This is a German proverb, which is translated into Russian as "Too many cooks spoil the child". At the beginning of the recording, the author describes the meaning of the proverb in several sentences. For example, he says: "Everyone always tries to keep me happy. Denn wenn most people with unterschiedlichen meinungen und methoden zusammen etwas machen wollen, kann das zu Schwierigkeiten führen". At first, the work is carried out individually. Everyone listens independently. As experience shows, various difficulties arise during collective listening. After this, the author begins the story. While listening, students make notes. The recording can be listened to 2-3 times. During the first listening, it is necessary to pay attention to the speed of the speaker's speech, his intonation, and try to understand the general meaning of the text. During the second listening, write down: "Who? Where? When? What did he do?" If the text turned out to be difficult or the speaker's speech is very fast, it is recommended to listen three times. After this, the teacher asks questions like - "richtig oder falsch" to find out how well the students understood the text. Then work is done in pairs. Students must retell the text to their interlocutor, ask and answer questions about the content. Thus, the ability to work in pairs is formed, which contributes to the development of dialogical speech.

But this site also has long audio recordings from 11 to 19 minutes, which are best listened to outside of class time, for example, at home. Working outside of class time develops the skill of

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independent work. For example, on the topic "Lernen an der Universität" the text lasts 9 minutes and the speaker's speech in this audio text is very fast. But the topic is very useful and has practical value for schoolchildren and students, because the speaker gives advice on studying: "How to prepare for exams?", "How to use an electronic library?", "Where to look for material?" etc.

Since students usually do this work at home, they can listen to the texts many times until they understand and extract the necessary information. Usually, everyone gets an individual task to check their understanding after listening. The tasks can be of the following type: prepare specific questions, correct and incorrect statements, print out a text with mistakes or a text with gaps, so the student must listen to the audio text carefully and write down every word so as not to miss the important ones. The advantage of working with "die deutsche Welle" is that the teacher can alternate audio texts from easy to difficult. For example, during the week they listen to easy and fairly short texts lasting 1-2 minutes, and before the weekend they give a recording of the average level so that the student has enough time to listen to the long material and write down the most important points in order to discuss them with the teacher in class after the weekend.

30 years ago, it was impossible to imagine that you could listen to a native speaker in real time, but today, thanks to new innovative technologies, we are given this opportunity, which makes learning a foreign language much easier and much more interesting.

Thus, at present it is impossible to imagine the educational process without the use of innovative pedagogical technologies. Such technologies are firmly established in the modern education system. Today, a foreign language teacher has a lot of opportunities that help to conduct their classes more interestingly and informatively. These opportunities contribute to more active students. Compared with the traditional teaching method, new implementations in training inevitably change the role of the teacher. Its task is to increase the independent work of students, support in the development of personality. Such training allows to increase motivation for learning, significantly increases interest in learning, and also gives good results in the formation of communication skills compared to the traditional method.

LITERATURE

1. Nazarova N. B., Mokhova O. L. New information technologies in teaching foreign languages // Modern problems of science and education. 2016. No. 3.

2. Application of SMART technologies in the educational process "Education without borders". MBOU "Secondary School No. 1". 2015. 20 p. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://infourok.ru/primenenie-smarttehnologii-v-obrazovatelnom-processe-mobu-soshobrazovanie-bez-granic-540134.html>

3. X. Kuchkinov (2023). MODERN METHODS AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN TEACHING ENGLISH. Science and innovation, 2 (B2), 155-158. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7630101

4. Kh. Kuchkinov (2022). MODERN METHODS OF STUDYING ENGLISH GRAMMAR. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 561-564. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7255635

5. Xudaybergan, K. (2023). METHODS OF LANGUAGE TEACHING TO AGRICULTURAL STUDENTS. *Ustozlar uchun*, 17(2), 136-139.

6. Valiqul o'g'li, Katayev Salaxiddin. "THE IMPORTANCE OF USING NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING ENGLISH LESSONS." *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА* 1.2 (2023):

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VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

7. Valiql o'g'li, K. S. (2023, October). ISSUES OF FORMING THE THINKING OF YOUTH IN THE PROCESS OF MODERNIZATION OF SOCIETY. In " *Conference on Universal Science Research 2023*" (Vol. 1, No. 10, pp. 32-35)

8. Katayev Salaxiddin Valiql o'g'li. (2023). NEW INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 30–36.

9. Katayev Salaxiddin Valiql o'g'li IMPORTANCE OF IELTS AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE. (2024). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(4),345=347.

10. Bobur Normamatovich Mengliyev. ***Problems of formation of pedagogical competence of physical education teachers.*** 4-25-2022.

11. Bobur Normamatovich Mengliyev. Trener-o'qituvchilar pedagogik kompetentligi va mahoratini shakllanishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning nazariy asoslari. June, 2023 y

12. Allamurodov Yigitali Abduqodirovich. (2022). WAYS OF MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT FOR AGRARIAN STUDENTS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(05), 195–199.
<https://doi.org/10.55640/eijmrms-02-05-37>

